

The Commodification of Bodily Disgust in TVCs Broadcast in Bangladesh: Manufacturing Sense of Disabilities by ‘Enforcing Normalcy’

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1. Introduction

The normal body [...] has shifted over to a new concept: the normal ideal. This normal ideal body is the one we see on the screen. It is the commodified body of the eroticized male or female star. This body is not actually the norm, but it is the fantasized, hypostatized body of commodified desire (Davis, 1995, p. 154).

The recurrence of such projection on the screen standardizes a norm for the body and when people eroticize this desire, they try to bring that norm in their own reality even if it may neither be necessary nor natural at all. If this expected normalized perfection is not met, the viewer begins to feel bad about his/her own body which may lead them to believe that the body and other physical features s/he owns is malfunctioning.

People tend to look for someone to prove their own superiority in the world of normalcy. Through this process, sometimes particular race, aspects, cultural conditions and even sometimes body parts are victimized. It is a common human tendency to identify an ‘Other’ to locate or construct self and assume superiority in self-identity and represent people and places that are different from us with a representational practice, which is known as stereotyping. According to Hall,

Stereotyping, in other words, is part of the maintenance of social

and symbolic order. It sets up a symbolic frontier between the ‘normal’ and the ‘deviant’, the ‘normal’ and the ‘pathological’, the ‘acceptable’ and the ‘unacceptable’, what ‘belongs’ and what does not or is ‘Other’, between ‘insiders’ and ‘outsiders’, Us and Them. It facilitates the ‘binding’ or bonding together of all of Us who are ‘normal’ into one ‘imagined community’; and it sends into symbolic exile all of Them - ‘the Others’ - who are in some way different - ‘beyond the pale’ (1997, p. 258).

Lennard J. Davis has used the notion of Jacques Lacan in order to derive to his idea of individual’s identity and notion of disability. According to Lacan, what human beings think of their identity is actually imaginary behind which the real subject resides. Since the birth of an infant, s/he bears that every image s/he has been seeing is something integrated to the self as a unified subject. When s/he finds himself or herself in the mirror, s/he gets the idea of his/her imaginary individual identity from the undefined fragmented mass. This idea of whole acts as the Lacanian ego. In this process the reality of being a whole subject is lost and the Freudian split comes to the action. As “the earliest experience of the body is actually of the fragmented body (corps moréle), the infant experiences his or her body as separate parts or pieces, as ‘turbulent movements’” (Lacan, 1977, p. 2). This concept of being a fragmented part resides into the unconscious and a constant fear of disintegration to fragmented body parts from the unconscious is always active. Davis applying this notion in terms of the whole body and fragmented body parts shows us that while confronting any human body which does not match with the ideal image of the whole body, the human psyche gets destabilized and challenged in fright. Because of the denied recognition, our dithered body parts work as abnormal or disabled organs from the perspective of ‘ideal normalcy’. The problem arises when this issue is sexualized on the visual media like television commercials by reiterating through in/pro-jecting an ideal image of a normal body. Through this process those who do not have the aspects and specific set of bodily features falls outside the line of normality and are ‘othered’ as ‘disable’.

2.1 Literature Review

Even though there is an extensive literature dedicated to the notion of minority and subaltern, disability studies has long been alienated from the mainstream focus of academia. In his study of the cultural assumptions prevailing human conception regarding people with disabilities, Lennard J. Davis focuses on disability studies by arguing forcefully against the 'ableist' discourse and advocates for a full re-forming of the category of disability itself. Davis shows how the modern society constructs its identity on the back of its physically disabled minority. Davis investigates "the pitfalls of privileging the figure of sight in conceptualizing the nature of textuality. And in a treatment of nudes and fragmented bodies in Western art, he shows how the ideal of physical wholeness is both demanded and denied in the classical aesthetics of representation" ("Enforcing Normalcy", n.d.). Michael L. Dorn in his review of the book *Enforcing Normalcy: Disability, Deafness and the Body* posits, "Disability presents itself to 'normal' people through two main modalities - function and appearance. In the functional modality, disability is conceived as inability to do something - walk, talk, hear, see, manipulate, and so on" and further adds, "The construction of disability is based on a deconstruction of a continuum[...]The person with disabilities is visualized, brought into the field of vision, and seen as a disabled person[...] Disability is a specular moment. The power of the gaze to control, limit, and patrol the disabled person is brought to the fore" (1995, p. 58). What also could not escape Davis' attention is the assumption of 'normality' that pervades the communication system.

According to D. M. Lowe,

The communications media of each period, whether oral, chirographic [written], typographic, or electronic, emphasize different senses or combinations of them, to support a different hierarchical organization of sensing. And the change in the culture of communications media ultimately leads to change in the hierarchy of sensing (Lowe 1982, p. 7).

We find the reflection of the abovementioned statement in Davis' book when Davis argues about how the notion of wholeness is constructed and recorded into the information system.

A good number of studies have been pursued on the construction of beauty standards and ideals in the media. In "Beauty, Body Image, and the Media", Mills, Shannon and Hogue have argued that,

Body image is a multidimensional construct that refers to one's perception of and attitudes about the size and shape of one's body. It has both a perceptual component that refers to how we see our body size, shape, weight, physical characteristics, performance, and movement, and an evaluative component, which refers to how we feel about these attributes and how those feelings influence our behaviours. Body dissatisfaction is experienced when one perceives that their body falls short of the societal ideal in terms of size and/or shape, regardless of a person's objective size or shape (2017, n.p.).

The body which differs from the enforced normal body is thus a body of dissatisfaction but this enforced ideal image is nothing but perceptual. It is the mass media that reinforces this process of enforcement through the repeated projection of the 'ideal image or wholeness'. Mills, Shannon and Hogue believe,

There is a robust empirical support for the idea that exposure to idealized body images in traditional forms of media (e.g. magazines and television) affects perceptions of beauty and appearance concerns by leading women to internalize a very slender female body type as ideal or beautiful. There is also support for the idea that exposure to the thin ideal is associated with body dissatisfaction in the moment among women (2017, n.p.).

According to them, it is the reiterated projection of the concept of beauty portrayed through an ideal body type which affect the perceptions of people regarding the notion of beauty and idea of wholeness. Aubrey and Frisby point out that, "Music videos offer a fertile ground to examine how beauty is defined and encoded,

considering they heavily emphasize "women's appearance and sexual appeal" (Aubrey & Frisby, 2011, p. 476) Again, Sut Jhally argues that music videos are the best place to scrutinize the relationship between a "woman's identity, her body, and her sexuality in a given culture" (Agbese, 2018, n.p.).

Much focus have been given on the objectification of woman, female body and the bodily features in advertisements and other media contents. A. Poorani writes,

Through the media we are constantly bombarded with the western images of "beautiful women" and "perfect bodies". Many surveys have proved the fact that men and women feel negative about their body image not only in the west but also in other parts of the world and the feminist scholars have tended that one should try to view the portrayal of idealized body image critically (2012).

Kapadia (2009) studied on the notion of body image among the Indian women which is shaped by the Indian media and examined how Indian women felt about their body size and ratio, what features affected how Indian women viewed their bodies, their observations of how women are pictured in Bollywood movies, and the impact of Bollywood on how Indian women perceived their bodies. Itisha Nagar and Rukhsana Virk (2017) also searched for the impact of media on constructing the body image of Indian woman. They also emphasized on the presentation of thin-shape body as the ideal one in media and how that creates an impact upon the lifestyle of the women in the given society. Hazir Ullah and Hifsa Nisar khan in their article "The Objectification of Women in Television Advertisements in Pakistan" examines "how television advertisements in Pakistan objectify women and idealize particular images of svelte, thin and soft female bodies as feminine capital" and argues, "the image of an ideal woman (as presented in advertisements and other popular textualizations) relegates women to mere objects of desire, leisure, sex, rather than people (human beings) with emotions and feelings" (2014, p. 24). As the concept of

disability comes from the idea of an ideal whole, Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe point out that, "every relation of representation is founded on a fiction: that of the presence at a certain level of something which is absent from it" (1989, p. 119). Thus, anything which will be missing from the ideal 'whole' would result into disability.

Hence, much of the focus have been given to the objectification of body and construction of an ideal image but not to the aftermath of such construction of an ideal image of the body. This paper by putting forward the aftermath and examining how disability factors are imposed through the recurring projection of certain television commercials in Bangladesh adds up to the existing body of knowledge.

2.2 Methodology

This study is a qualitative critical discourse analysis and library research. Discourse analysis as a method is used to analyze any form of text like written, oral, visual or sign language. Data are collected from contents like advertisements, books, research articles with a focus on how modern advertisements advocate to manufacture sense of disability through the projected contrast of the pre and post consumption stages of the product. Here, the texts refer to the selected advertisements in which I study the notion of commodifying bodily disgust. After identifying the notions in these texts, I analyze how certain notions are being communicated to evoke a sense of 'normalcy' in the audio-visual media broadcast in Bangladesh. It further focuses on the issue of how these depicted conception of 'normalcy' is manufacturing a sense of disability at the same time.

2.3 Rationale and Limitations

This research is going to explore how the notion of normalcy is constructed in the audio-visual advertisements broadcast in Bangladesh and how the sense of disability is being imposed at the

same time. This paper contributes to a better understanding of the how disabilities are manufactured through commodifying the bodily disgust for the sake of advertisement. It also helps us to understand how certain bodily features are undermined to evoke a psychological fear in order to increase the sale of the commodity.

Due to the word and time restraint, the research will only focus on the advertisements broadcast in Bangladesh. It only takes accounts of the advertisements where we get a before after comparison of the pre and post consumed stage of the commodity.

3. TVCs Enforcing Normalcy and Imposing Disability Factor

Visual media has become one of the major sources of entertainment for the subcontinental people and it is more available than any other form of entertainment. In Bangladesh, a huge number of population have access to television and depends on its content for entertainment rather than going out. For this huge amount of consumption of the broadcast visual contents of television, the product manufacturing companies finds this medium suitable for advertising. As women are already thought as inferior than men in the society and there is even a tendency to objectify women, the television commercial agencies purposefully take advantages of this cultural assumption and its effect of a consistent fear of women in order to create commercials and try to evoke the sense that with the use of that very product they are advertising for will be able to enable them to be privileged and successful in the society. So, for the sake of consumerism, visual media is selling bodily disgust or suppression through these commercials.

3.1 Dove Deodorant TVC Commodifying Bodily Disgust

The dubbed version of the video commercial of “New Dove Whitening Deodorant” which has been broadcast in Bangladeshi television channels visualizes a number of young

Figure 1: Four sequences of the video commercial of “New Dove Whitening Deodorant”

women hesitating to show their underarms. It portrays the shame of having a dark skinned underarms in the collective psyche of the society. Those women seem to hide their underarms for not being perfectly fair that matches the complexion of their face and after using the product, when they get the perfect underarms which they can show off to everyone, they seem to be more confident, projected as more cheerful in flaunting their underarms. This creates an idealized image of a body part and sets up a standard for women to have perfectly fair skinned underarms in order to wear sleeveless and show off the it to others. It almost seems that having a perfectly whitened underarm is a license to wear sleeveless dresses. This projection tends to establish the idea that having darkened underarms are something which bears shame and tries to make it a taboo. The constant fear of being gazed upon impacts on the psyches of the women having dark-skin underarms and they tend to identify themselves as not being ‘whole’ but ‘fragmented’ for not having the proper skin toned underarms. This identification of ‘fragmented self’ makes them disable. Thus, having dark underarms which can be a natural phenomenon is confronted with disgust which ‘otherizes’ the pre-consumption stage of the projected person or those people who has such features and makes them disable in the lens of the society.

3.2 Nivea Whitening Deodorant ‘Enforcing Normalcy’ through the Objectification of Body Parts

In another television commercial of “Nivea Whitening Deo”, we can find a similar projection in a rather different narrative. In the video commercial we find that, the previously used other deodorants are shown as reasons of darker underarms of a woman, whereas only fairer underarms are and can be exposed. The actress in the commercial exposes this particular body part to impress the male partner because she has more confidence as she has fairer underarms. This not only make the exposed part prone to the male gaze but also shows how she is a representation of “Wholeness” constructed by the gazes of his partner. What even more problematic is the slogan of the commercial “go sleeveless on him” which gives more importance to the spectacle of male chauvinist society. As Mulvey states,

Figure 2: 6 sequences of “Nivea Whitening Sensitive Deo” TVC

“In their traditional exhibitionist role women are simultaneously looked at and displayed, with their appearance coded for strong visual and erotic impact so that they can be said to connote to-be-looked-at-ness” (1999, p. 62). So, the identity which is but an “illusion of wholeness” is constructed through this eroticized male gaze. But the reiteration of such visual projection essentially marginalizes those who have such bodily condition of dark skinned underarms with a sense of disgust and shame. This encoded disgust in the visual commercials make these people ‘disable’ in the eyes of the society.

3.3 Fair & Lovely TVC Imposing Disability Factor Upon Both Women & Men’s Dark Skin

The third television commercial that I have included in the study is a the popular “Fair and Lovely Fairness Treatment Cream”

Figure 3: 6 sequences of “Fair & Lovely Fairness Treatment Cream” TVC

commercial. Here we can find the before-after comparison narrative too. In the beginning, we find a projection of the uglier version of a girl who is also unsuccessful in her career. Being profoundly concerned about his daughter's future, the father tries to convince her to accept a marriage proposal from a successful man. Being depressed under such situation, she meets with a friend who suggests her to use the product, i.e, the Fair and Lovely Fairness Cream in order to get rid of her problems. After using the product, she becomes fairer which not only bears the implied message that fair skin is a beauty standard but also presents that darker skin girls are ugly and have no value and future other than being a 'marriage material' in the subcontinental context. Thus, through such problematic projection of before-after narrative, such bodily feature of darker skin is demeaned and the commercials are depicting bodily disgust to impose a sense of insecurity and 'inferiorize' the people with dark underarms in order to increase the sale of their product. Through this process, the TV commercials are not only commodifying on bodily disgust but also establishing the notion that darker skin women are 'disabled' in the eye of the society.

The racial demeaning of darkened and commodify the bodily disgust to evoke psychological fear and increase the sales of the product is not limited to only women's fairness cream adverts but also in male fairness cream advertisements as well. In the dubbed advertisement of "Fair & Lovely Men", we can find that the star actor Shah Rukh Khan is advocating for this fairness cream and suggesting another man to use it who has darker skin. The projection implies that for having darker skin, the man is not getting enough attention and thus, this commercial, too, feeds on to bodily disgust to evoke a sense of fear of having darker skin and connects the problematic notion of being unsuccessful for being such. Playing on such psychological of the audience, the companies commodifies the bodily disgust as their selling point and in the process normalizes and idolizes the idea that skin complexion must have to be fair and without fair skin one can neither be attractive nor be successful.

Figure 4: 4 sequences of "Fair & Lovely Men Fairness Treatment Cream" TVC

3.4 Godrej Expert Hair Colour TVC Depicting Disgust for Grey Hairs

In the TVC of Godrej Expert Hair Colour, again we get a before after consumption stage comparison in order to propagate the bodily disgust of having grey hair. In the commercial we find that celebrity Bangladeshi cricket star Mashrafe Bin Murtaza enters in a party and getting attention. Then a woman who is attending the party with her partner asks for a selfie with Mashrafe but as her partner who has grey hair and looks a bit older due to his hair poses to be with them in the selfie the woman disrespectfully says that, "Hey go away! You're increasing the age of the whole picture." Then Mashrafe suggests that man to use the product for which his hair becomes black and he starts to look younger. Thus, on a next occasion, while taking another selfie with Mashrafe again his female partner says that, "I do not take any photo without you", which implies the attractiveness of the post-consumption stage.

Such TV commercial's strategy while advocating and advertising for the use of their product demeans a natural bodily feature in the prior consumption state. As the man does not get to be a part of the selfie for having grey hair in the first instance, the advertisement

incorporates a sense of revulsion to the feature of having grey hair and generates a fear among the male audience of being excluded

Figure 5: 6 sequences of “Godrej Expert Hair Colour” TVC

from such social gathering for having grey hairs. From a fear of being excluded from such social gatherings, one would buy and consume the product- that being the strategy of their marketing also implies that grey hair people are excluded and attempts to normalize the fact that one must have black hair to get a license to be in a photo at a social gathering or party.

3.5 Complan Health Drink TVC Demeaning Shorter Height

The notion of bodily disgust can not only be found in the commercials of cosmetic products but also in products like health drinks. In the television commercial of Complan Health Drinks, a

kid is portrayed to be bullied before his mother by other kids for not being tall. After consulting a doctor, the mother gives her son to drink Complan Health Drink regularly for which he later becomes taller than all the other kids and takes pride of his post-consumption state before another kid as he has become taller now. The act can be also seen as revengeful as this kid can also be found to make fun of the another kid who appeared in the latter part of the video. So, here being of shorter height is projected as something demeaning. The commercial is selling the bodily disgust of having short height and evoking a fear to the mother that her child might not grow in a ‘normal’ height without that drink and might fall prone to bullies as a result. Thus, again through commodifying the bodily disgust of having a short height, the commercials are not only increasing the sale of the commodity, the commercial also enforces us to normalize that having short height is something negative which can people make fun of. By doing such, the

Figure 6: 4 sequences of “Complan Drink” TVC

commercials are constructing the notion of proper height and are marginalizing those children who do not have such height. But in real world, we can see that the height does not only depend upon

the nutrition facts but also upon heredity. So, in the process of creating such bodily disgust and evoking fear, they are ‘otherizing’ the kids with less height as disable.

4. Consumerism in Constructing the Ideology to Dominate the Marginalized ‘Other’

If we look at those advertisements, we would find the post-industrial crisis of expansion of consumption. It has become ‘pastiche’ to target women by showing off an explosive beautiful body to increase the marketing policy. Even where the male product should be the main concern, female models are used in an offensive way to increase the projection of lucrativeness of a man. This capitalist society can definitely increase the consumption of the product either giving the price of women’s dissatisfaction over their own body or representing them as an object where man is the subject. Inside every woman they create dissatisfaction for the sake of consumption where everything becomes a commodity including knowledge, because it develops a particular type of knowledge which can determine ideology in a society. In other areas, they are reiterating bodily disgust and creating fear among the audience by demeaning specific bodily features which can as well be natural in real life. Darker skin, under arm patches, shorter heights are always presented negatively in the commercials which attempts to construct a stereotyped ideology in the society. At the end of the day this ideology would matter even more than the product or consumption. The society of spectacle would change with this ideology which is directly connected to visual media. According to Marxist critic Althusser, “Ideology is a system of representations (images, myths, ideas or concepts according to the case) endowed with an existence and an historical role at the heart of a given society.” (157) So, the system of representation at the heart of a given society can create any definition from these representations which can define a whole culture. It is alarming for our own society where specific aspects of body are represented in such a discourteous manner.

When it comes to the representation of women, the power politics of message plays an important role, because at some point this message would turn into knowledge and gradually a discourse. These visual representations would give a message in our culture and would affectively change the female point of view about the “ideal normal” body which creates a stereotyped knowledge about women as well as determining their identity. These advertisements successfully create a visual normalcy inside all the women as well as males in the subcontinent. According to Foucault’s “power/knowledge” relation: “a discourse produces through different practices of representations (scholarship, exhibition, literature, painting etc.), a form of racialized knowledge of the Other (Orientalism) deeply implicated in the operations of power (imperialism)” (Hall, 1997, p. 260). So, this message creates knowledge and knowledge is able to create power to dominate the marginalized other in the society.

5. TVCs Manufacturing Sense of Disabilities by Enforcing ‘Normalcy’

These advertisements try to present and construct the notion that selected bodily features are unusual and not to be shown off. While the body is a natural combination of all the body parts and features, each part and feature deserve equal values. But we tend to classify these bodily features and parts by ranking them on the basis of a constructed spectacle. There are certain norms or codes that define whether something is normal i.e. usual or not. Based on these constructed societal normalcy, we tend to categorize our body parts as good or bad, beautiful or ugly, appealing or unappealing. And it is the television commercials which can be considered as agents to create discriminations and regulate the status of beautiful perfect and normal body parts. The commercials make people fantasize about the ideal bodily aspects and people not only gaze negatively upon those features which is portrayed as disgusting but also tries to achieve that look of the fantasy. As one is unable to achieve that ideal ‘wholeness’ or

perfection in bodily aspects, one is confronted with Lacanian fragmented body parts and thinks himself or herself as not complete. This is how the commercials through enforcing normalcy makes these people disable. But as Davis argues, “wholeness is a hallucination” (1995, p. 139), the ideal normal is also a hallucination. On the basis of this hallucination such bodily features are being victimized on the television media where the perfect body and this identity is determined most of the time from a consumerist capitalistic point of view.

6. Conclusion

In this age of mass media, visual media is becoming increasingly available and are easily adapted due to its passive interface system of viewing a content among any type of people in the world. Through this mass media, any kind of message can be disseminated to the world and thus to the masses. Therefore, it is the responsibility of a particular society to examine what contents they are disseminating and want to represent to the world with. The representation of such bodily disgust, through this power politics of consumerist society can make benefit for the manufacturers, but the imposition of sense of disability, be it symbolic or direct, is unjust and the price is to be paid for this by our society and culture would be far more than the momentarily benefit made by this manufacturer class.

References

- Addworldme. (2010, March 26). Complian TV ad [Video File]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VBejMUB5sC0>
- Agbese, A. (2018). Beauty Ideals and Media: Constructing the Ideal Image for Nigerian Women through Music Videos. *Media Report on Women*, Vol. 46, Issue 1. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: <https://www.ques-tia.com/magazine/1P4-2001349489/beauty-ideals-and-media-constructing-the-ideal-image>
- Aubrey, J. S. and Frisby, C. M. (2011). Sexual Objectification in Music Videos: A Content Analysis Comparing Gender and Genre. *Mass Communication and Society*, Vol. 14, Issue. 4. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/233027814_Sexual_Objectification_in_Music_Videos_A_Content_Analysis_Comparing_Gender_and_Genre
- Barry, P. (2002). *Beginning Theory: An Introduction to Literary and Cultural Theory*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Davis, L. (1995). *Enforcing Normalcy: Disability, Deafness and the Body*. New York: Verso.
- Davis, L. (2001). Nude Venuses, Medusa’s Body, and Phantom Limbs: Disability and Visuality. In Mitchell, D. and Snyder, S. (Eds.) *The Body and Physical Difference: Discourse of Disability*. Michigan: University of Michigan Press.
- Dove India. (2013, Jan 3). New Dove Whitening Deodorant [Video File]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nR9GiNXpB1s>
- Dorn, M. L. (1995). Book Review: Lennard J. Davis’ *Enforcing Normalcy: Disability, Deafness and the Body*. New York: Verso. *disClosure: A Journal of Social Theory*: Vol. 6, Article 4. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: <https://uknowledge.uky.edu/disclosure/vol6/iss1/4/>
- Emami Bangladesh. (2018, Dec 25). Fair and Handsome Fairness Cream Thematic TVC Bangladesh 15 Sec. [Video File]. Retrieved from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=97Ac0_jfiKY
- Enforcing Normalcy. (n.d.). In Verso Books. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: <https://www.versobooks.com/books/677-enforcing-normalcy>
- Everything About Ads. (2016, April 23). Fair and Lovely Fairness Cream Advertisement [Video File]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mhv5PmAG190>

- Godrej Bangladesh. (2017, Dec 25). Godrej Expert Hair Color TV AD_Mashrafe Mortaza [Video File]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yevvjXJBwa8>
- Hall, S. (1997). The Spectacle of the 'Other'. In *Representation: Cultural Representations and Signifying Practices*. London: Sage Publications.
- Lacan, J. (1977). *Ecrits: A Selection*. Translated by Alan Sheridan. New York: Norton.
- Lowe, D.M. (1982). *The History of Bourgeois Perception*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Mills, S.; Shannon, A. and Hogue, J. (2017). Beauty, Body Image, and the Media. In Martha Levine (ed.) *Perception of Beauty*. Rijeka: InTech.
- Mulvey, L. (1999). Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema. In Leo Braudy and Marshall Cohen (eds.) *Film Theory and Criticism: Introductory Readings*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Nagar, I and Virk, R. (2017). The Struggle Between the Real and Ideal: Impact of Acute Media Exposure on Body Image of Young Indian Women. *Sage Open Access Journal*. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244017691327>
- Nivea India. (2014, April 28). NIVEA Whitening Sensitive Deodorant -- 0% Alcohol – Anushka Sharma English TVC [Video File]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TKI2mRnHqoE>
- Poorani, A. (2012). Who determines the ideal body? A Summary of Research Findings on Body Image. *New Media and Mass Communication*, Vol. 2. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.880.1092&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Ullah, H and Khan, H. N. (2014). The Objectification of Women in Television Advertisements in Pakistan. *FWU Journal of Social Science*, Vol. 8, No. 2. Retrieved 22 June, 2019 from World Wide Web: <http://sbbwu.edu.pk/journal/FWUJourn>

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cation%20of%20Women%20in%20Television.pdf

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